

References

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Effects of salt and osmotic stress on free polyamine accumulation in moderately salt-resistant rice cultivar Aiwu

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Polyamines (putrescine, spermidine, and spermine) are ubiquitous and positively charged compounds involved in the control of plant growth and development and in the response to several biotic and abiotic stresses. Data on polyamine accumulation in salt-stressed rice are contradictory and generally deal with exposure of several days to NaCl only. Our aim was to determine whether the ionic or osmotic component of salt stress is involved in the initial steps of polyamine accumulation in rice.

Twenty-five-day-old plants of cultivar Aiwu maintained on nutrient solution (Yoshida et al 1976) in a phytotron (light intensity: 300 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, 12 h d^{-1} , 70% relative humidity, and 30/25 °C day/night temperatures) were exposed to isoosmotic concentrations of NaCl or KCl (50 and 100 mM) or PEG (polyethylene glycol 6000; 16% and 26%). These stressing agents induced a decrease in osmotic potential of nutrient solution corresponding to -0.12 and -0.25 MPa for the two stress intensities, respectively. Stress imposition corre-

sponded to the beginning of the light period and plants were collected after 3 and 12 h of exposure. Osmotic potential (ψ_s) and ion content were quantified separately on roots and shoots using a vapor pressure osmometer (Wescor) and an inductively coupled argon plasma emission spectrophotometer according to Lutts et al (1999). Endogenous free polyamine was quantified by a Shimadzu RF-10Axl fluorimeter after separation by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) according to Aziz et al (1999).

Dry weight percentages (DW; in %), osmotic potential ψ_s (in MPa), Na^+ and K^+ concentrations (in mmol g^{-1} DW) in roots and shoots of plants exposed for 3 or 12 h to isoosmotic concentrations of NaCl or KCl (50 or 100 mM) or PEG (16% or 26%). The two stress intensities correspond to an induced decrease in osmotic potential of nutrient solution of -0.12 and -0.25 MPa, respectively. Values are means of eight replicates per treatment: for a given parameter, means of the same line followed by the same letter are not significantly different at $P = 0.05$, according to the method of Duncan using the MSTAT-C system (Michigan State University).

		-0.12 MPa				-0.25 MPa		
		Control	50 mM NaCl	50 mM KCl	16% PEG	100 mM NaCl	100 mM KCl	26% PEG
Roots	3 h							
	DW	14.80 a	19.30 b	16.60 a	21.80 b	29.60 c	14.50 a	23.50 b
	ψ_s	-0.32 a	-0.57 b	-0.58 b	-0.32 a	-0.62 b	-0.73 c	-0.35 a
	Na^+	0.07 a	0.37 b	0.12 a	0.06 a	0.63 c	0.07 a	0.08 a
	K^+	0.84 a	0.93 a	1.31 b	0.76 a	0.86 a	1.85 c	0.69 a
	12 h							
	DW	13.90 a	18.10 b	11.40 a	20.50 b	22.10 b	11.70 a	22.80 b
	ψ_s	-0.31 a	-0.53 b	-0.37 a	-0.25 a	-0.45 b	-0.35 a	-0.37 a
Na^+	0.08 a	0.82 b	0.08 a	0.11 a	0.75 b	0.13 a	0.09 a	
K^+	0.62 a	0.96 b	1.67 c	0.57 a	1.09 b	3.02 c	0.67 b	
Shoots	3 h							
	DW	17.30 a	18.00 a	17.40 a	19.80 a	19.20 a	19.50 a	21.80 b
	ψ_s	-1.02 a	-1.16 a	-1.12 a	-1.34 b	-1.05 a	-1.17 a	-1.31 b
	Na^+	0.03 a	0.13 b	0.05 a	0.03 a	0.17 c	0.02 a	0.03 a
	K^+	1.24 a	1.32 a	1.46 b	1.09 a	1.15 a	1.43 b	0.98 a
	12 h							
	DW	16.30 a	16.60 a	18.30 a	24.20 b	20.10 a	20.40 a	25.30 b
	ψ_s	-1.64 a	-1.66 a	-1.63 a	-2.08 b	-1.57 a	-1.50 a	-2.46 c
Na^+	0.05 a	0.16 b	0.03 a	0.04 a	0.19 b	0.04 a	0.03 a	
K^+	1.13 a	1.15 a	1.29 b	0.91 a	1.19 a	1.61 c	0.97 a	

Polyamine concentration (nmol g⁻¹ fresh weight)

Putrescine (Put), spermidine (Spd), and spermine (Spm) concentrations in shoots of plants exposed for 3 or 12 h to isoosmotic concentrations of NaCl, KCl, or PEG. Two concentrations of stressing agent were used: 50 mM NaCl or KCl and 16% PEG induced a decrease in the osmotic potential of -0.12 MPa in nutrient solution, whereas 100 mM NaCl or KCl and 26% PEG induced a decrease of -0.25 MPa. Each value is the mean of eight replicates and vertical bars are S.E.

Dry weight percentages increased at the root level after 3 h of exposure to NaCl or PEG but these were not affected by KCl. A slight increase in dry weight percentages at the shoot level was observed in all treatments but was statistically significant for PEG only (see table). Similarly, the shoot

ys strongly decreased after 12 h of exposure to 26% PEG, while the root ys decreased in response to ionic stresses; such a decrease was more marked during the first few hours of exposure (3 h) than at the end of the treatment (12 h). Endogenous concentrations of Na⁺ and K⁺ increased in both roots and shoots after 3 h of exposure to NaCl and KCl, respectively,

while PEG had no effect on mineral nutrition. Root (data not shown) and shoot (see figure) putrescine concentration increased after 3 h of exposure to ionic stresses but remained unaffected in the presence of PEG. At the shoot level, spermidine concentration was also lower, in most cases, in response to PEG compared with ionic stresses. Spermidine significantly increased after 12 h of exposure to the highest dose of NaCl or KCl only. In both roots and shoots, putrescine accumulation was associated with a slight increase in agmatine content, suggesting a stress-induced stimulation of arginine decarboxylase (data not shown). We conclude that polyamine accumulation in rice may occur rapidly after the beginning of salt stress exposure and does not require any osmotic signal, at least at the shoot level.

References

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Tungro screen kits for national programs

The diagnosis of two viruses associated with the highly damaging tungro disease—rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV)—is based mainly on the orange-yellow leaf discoloration symptoms exhibited on susceptible cultivars. Some of these cultivars, however, do not produce these symptoms in the field under experimental conditions.

A simple, cheap, rapid, and reliable method for detecting tungro viruses such as RTBV in rice was developed at IRRI in cooperation with the Natural Resources Institute (UK) for national programs. RTBV antisera was successfully used following a double cross-adsorption process that overcomes the problem of cross-reaction to healthy plant components. The prototype diagnostic kit was tested in the field in Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, and the Philippines. Results have shown that the kit was effective in confirming the presence of RTBV in rice samples collected from the field. The kit also had a good degree of accuracy.

This robust tool is expected to greatly facilitate tungro resistance breeding programs and has further applications for epidemiological studies and for field monitoring. Further refinement should make the kit an invaluable tool for use by rice breeders, plant pathologists, and crop protection specialists in many countries in South and Southeast Asia where tungro remains a persistent and major problem. The kit provides researchers and farmers with a quick decision-making tool to take appropriate control measures in response to emerging pest outbreaks.

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